

Synthesis of Antibacterial Non-toxic 1,4-Thiazolidinones

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Sixteen 1,4-thiazolidinones, obtained by cyclocondensation of ketoanils (including isomers) with thioglycolic acid, have been characterised for their non-toxic and antibacterial properties.

Diverse effects¹ of thiazolidinones on biological systems have evoked considerable interest and a large number of such heterocyclics, obtained from Schiff's bases, have been worked out. Keeping in view the biological importance of these compounds, a few cyclocondensation products of ketoanils with thioglycolic acid, which have not been described hitherto, have been characterised and studied for their toxic and bacterial properties and reported in the present paper.

Results and Discussion

Physical data consistent with formulae of thiazolidinones are noted in Table 1. Infrared spectra display characteristic bands at ca. 1724 (C=O ring), 1571 (C-N) and 674 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C of thiazolidinone ring). Other peaks appearing at ca. 1660, 3112, 2669, 1059, 1267, 1208 and ca. 1351 cm⁻¹ attributable² respectively to $\nu_{C=O}$ (acyclic/chain), ν_{C-OH} (intramolecularly bonded), δ_{OH} (enolic) and ν_{C-O} , ν_{OH} (phenolic) and ν_{C-O} , which indicate co-existence of enolic structures (2, 3 and/or 4) with ketonic structures (1 and/or 3). To check this possibility, nmr spectrum of *p*-aminodiethylthiazolidinone (as a typical example) was examined. Peaks corresponding to CH-N/CH-S, CH₂ (ring) and phenolic groups occur² at τ 2.25, 6.45 and 3.25 respectively. Besides a doublet at τ 3.35 due to acyclic conjugated and benzenoid protons indicate 2, 3 and/or 4 structures alongwith 1 and/or 2 and support the ir spectral inference. An additional peak at τ 6.0, however, is not accountable at present.

TABLE I - PHYSICAL DATA OF THIAZOLIDINONES

Sl no	R	Colour	M p °C	Yield %
1	C ₆ H ₅	Dark brown	95*	54
2	C ₆ H ₄ -SH- <i>o</i>	Brown	85	47
3	C ₅ H ₄ N- <i>o</i>	Black	-	67
4	C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>o</i> H ₂ O	Mustard yellow	65	40
5	C ₆ H ₄ -NO ₂ - <i>p</i> 2H ₂ O	Green yellow	116	57
6	C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>o</i>	Black	83	43
7	C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>m</i>	Mustard yellow	105	46
8	C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₃ - <i>p</i>	Brown yellow	82	49
9	C ₁₀ H ₇ - α	Black	56	68
10	C ₁₀ H ₇ - β	Brown	62	60
11	C ₆ H ₄ -Cl- <i>p</i>	Black	140	53
12	C ₆ H ₄ -Br- <i>p</i> 2H ₂ O	Brown yellow	118	57
13	C ₆ H ₄ -N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ - <i>p</i>	Black	80	58
14	C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₃ - <i>p</i>	Brown	152	56
15	X-C ₆ H ₄ -X- <i>p</i> H ₂ O	Black	-	63
16	X-C ₆ H ₄ -C ₆ H ₄ -X- <i>p</i> H ₂ O	Brown	171	59

X = Thiazolidinone skeleton

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

Yields of the isomeric products, which are in opposite orders of $\nu_{C=O}$ (ring) and ν_{C-N} values, are in accordance with the position of substituents (*o*-, *m*-, *p*- and β -, α -).

Although all the compounds showed good activity against both the bacteria examined (inhibition zone 7-13 mm) in all the four dilutions, sample nos. 4 and 3, and 10 (Table 1) were selective to *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* respectively.

Toxicity experiments on albino mice showed non-toxic nature of the compounds, as all the mice

survived normally, except sample nos. 2, 5, 6, 8 and 10 (Table 1) which showed positive and negative results as one of the mice in each pair died. Sample nos. 1, 12 and 15 showed gnawing property as albino mice started abnormal biting and running movements whereas sample nos. 6, 9 and 14 had positive hypnotic and sedative effects. No toxic effect could be observed during these experiments.

Experimental

Ketonils were synthesised by reacting *o*-hydroxyphenylglyoxal with primary amines in ether as reported earlier³.

1,4-Thiazolidinones were prepared by refluxing a mixture of thioglycolic acid (0.01 mol) and the ketoanil (0.01 mol; 0.005 mol of bisketoanil) for 15–20 h on a water-bath. Concentrated reaction mixture was then neutralised with aqueous solution of NaHCO₃ to remove excess acid. The resulting solid were washed with water and dried in a hot air-oven at ~ 60°. After ascertaining their homogeneity by tlc, all the products were purified by column chromatography using silica gel G as adsorbent and acetone as resolving solvent.

Melting points were determined in the open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. All the samples were analysed for the elements microanalytically at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and nmr spectrum (acetone) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer.

Antibacterial activity test was carried out *in vitro* against gram-positive *S. aureus* and gram-negative *E. coli* by agar-plate diffusion method⁴

in DMF at 100, 80, 60 and 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations in Mullar-Hinton medium. For toxicity, a test sample solution in aqueous alcohol (3 : 2, v/v) was given in 1 mg kg^{-1} dose intraperitoneally to a pair of albino mice either sex (25–45 g) and after 24 h the mortality was observed.

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